

GeoComBi - Geospatial context enriched image annotation in BIIGLE 2.0

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Abstract

Imaging with drones and other platforms has become a data source of growing importance in Earth Sciences and other related fields of research. Online image analysis and annotation platforms has become important tools to identify objects / regions of interest either manually or with machine learning methods (sometimes related to as AI). In the latter case, the manual annotations are of substantial importance for the learning algorithms. But the inspection of single images and the annotation results is usually done without a larger geospatial context. In this project we implemented two new visualization functions for the open source image and video annotation tool BIIGLE 2.0 (GPL 3.0 license, > 4,000 registered users) that address this gap. The first function supports users to visualize the positions of the images in a map, uploaded to the BIIGLE system. The second function allows for the first time to display a co-registered mosaic as a background for the single images during the annotation process. These functions enable users to analyze the images in a larger geospatial context. Future developments can now address further improvements like implementing interfaces to data servers or improved feature to interactively tune the visualization of the maps / mosaics.

I. Introduction

In the last 20 years, digital imaging and video (in the remainder we will use the term “visual data” that relates to digital images and video) in the context of earth sciences and related fields (such as marine biology, biodiversity, ecology) has evolved due to several technical advances. Nowadays, large areas and habitats are inspected with remotely controlled vehicles (e.g. ROV (remotely operated vehicle) or UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle)) or

autonomous vehicles (e.g. AUV (Autonomous Underwater Vehicle)) and terabytes of visual data can be collected in a single exploration or monitoring/exploration campaign. The analysis of the visual data includes different kinds of semantic interpretation and annotation steps like assigning the whole image or a region of interest to a semantic category, which could be a habitat category, an event category, a species description/morphotype/taxonomy or something else. This process is time-consuming and requires domain experience. As the recorded data keeps growing in volume and resolution and the number of expert time for interpretation is limited, a serious bottleneck situation has arisen. To make the visual data analysis more efficient and effective, online image/video annotation tools have been proposed that allow users to share data, annotate data with standardized catalogs, visualize results and export the results as spreadsheets for subsequent statistical analysis. Among the most prominent tools that represent the state of the art in this area are VIAME, CoralNet and BIIGLE 2.0 (www.biigle.de) [Langenkämper et al. 2017, Zurowicz et al. 2021], which has been developed by the Biodata Mining Group at Bielefeld University in Germany. However, although the visual inspection and semantic annotation is now supported by such tools and some of them even offer machine learning modules to automate some steps in the annotation, the tools do not support an integrative analysis of geospatial information and visual data. In practice, the images were annotated in BIIGLE and the data was exported as spread sheets and fed into another geospatial visualization afterwards. Neither in BIIGLE nor in other related annotation tools it was possible to visually link one single image or a set of images to the geospatial location in a map or in a mosaic. To close this aforementioned gap and to enable a geospatial context-aware browsing, interpretation and annotation of single images we started the GeoComBi project, supported as a NFDI4Earth pilot. We developed two new BIIGLE 2.0 functions that now allow all BIIGLE users including geospatial context information in the interpretation of visual data. Linking the image interpretation step to information about the large scale profile of the landscape / sea floor has the potential to accelerate the analysis by geospatial filtering, to support an early interpretation of the geospatial layout of annotated species or to support the decision in object classification by integrating morphological visual features and geospatial features displayed. The first function is referred to as **Geospatial browsing and filtering**. Using BIIGLE's filter tab now allows users to display a map together for instance with the positions of images in the volume. This map display can be used to display all images available so that users can select a subset condition for geospatial features or to select a subset of images. The second function is referred to as **Geospatial context fusion display**. Here, a geographically linked mosaic can be displayed as surrounding "background" information for a selected image and its annotations.

II. Results

a) Implemented Solution

Within the pilot, we focused on the development of two new features (1. Geospatial browsing and filtering mechanism, 2. Geospatial context fusion display) and an accompanying upload mechanism in order to integrate geospatial information in the BIIGLE 2.0¹ software.

1. Geospatial browsing and filtering mechanism

¹ henceforth BIIGLE

This new feature allows users to link one volume to one (or more) maps. If the images contained in a volume are associated with geospatial coordinates (within the image headers or via metadata files such as iFDOs²), users can now apply a geospatial filter to the image volume (i.e. search for a (sub)set of images within the volume). Selecting the new filter opens a map-interface containing the geo-located images (see Figure 1 below). This interface enables users to select a subset condition for geospatial features or to select a subset of images after the annotation (for instance filtering all images showing a particular species) and visualize the positions of these images in the map.

Figure 1: Shows the map-interface of the “geo-selection” filter (opens up once the filter is selected and added). By clicking on the filter-button on the volume overview page, the “geo-selection” filter can be selected from the list of filters.

The map-interface comes with the additional functionality to display the previously uploaded and linked maps. These can be enabled/disabled through clicking on the corresponding “geo-overlay” in the list (see Figure 2 below). This functionality allows users to integrate geospatial features relevant to their research, e.g. by incorporating the large scale profile of the landscape / sea

floor in form of an image-mosaic or a bathymetric map.

² iFDOs = image FAIR Digital Objects

Figure 2: Map interface with geo-located images (blue dots) and example mosaic overlay. On the right hand side, the available associated “geo-overlays” are shown (either uploaded as geoTIFF or linked as WMS). These can be displayed on the map by selecting/deselecting each overlay.

2. Geospatial context fusion display

This new feature aims at supporting the decision making process in the object classification task by providing geospatial context information in the image annotation tool of BIIGLE. We realized this feature by implementing a visualization function which displays a georeferenced grid as context layer³ below the single image in the image annotation view (see Figure 3 below).

³ surrounding “background” information around the computed position of the current image and/or annotations

Figure 3: The annotation view in BIIGLE with context-layer in form of a georeferenced photo-mosaic. The red frame is not part of the visualization in BIIGLE, it is merely added to mark the currently displayed single image within the context-layer.

Based on the provided metadata of both sources, the position and rotation of the context-layer with regard to the image is calculated and adjusted such that both sources are aligned. The scale of the two sources can be aligned in a similar fashion. But as a prerequisite, the pixel-to-unit ratio's of both sources are needed, which are less likely to be contained in the metadata as compared to, e.g., the geo-coordinates or yaw (a.k.a. rotation of the image in the mosaic). Therefore, a manual option to adjust the scale of the context-layer was added (see Figure 4). The context-layer opacity can be adjusted, too. And similar to the browsing feature, it is possible to choose a context-layer to be displayed from the list of available layers.

Figure 4: Showing a slightly transparent context layer and the possible adjustments in the settings-tab of the image annotation view. Below the “Geo Overlay Opacity” slider, a list of available context-layers is displayed. Below that is the Edit-Button to adjust the scale of the context-layer. Once the button is pressed and the mouse is located on the annotation view, users can adjust the scale by using the mouse-wheel/trackpad and confirm with another button-press.

3. Upload Mechanism

In order to upload the geo-overlays that are then used in the new features, an upload panel was added to the BIIGLE system. In this new panel, overlays can be created by uploading geoTIFF-files or linking web-map-services (WMS) via URL's. We discussed with our partners at GEOMAR to integrate the two options, as both are common approaches to make georeferenced grids available.

The panel was placed in the volume edit view (see Figure 5). In the geoTIFF tab, an overlay can be uploaded as a geoTIFF file (in .tif or .tiff format). In the WMS tab, an overlay can be embedded by providing the URL to a WMS source. Either through a base URL, (e.g. <https://maps.org/geoserver/namespace/wms>), which will then determine the first layer of the WMS as the overlay, or by providing a different URL including query parameters (e.g. <https://maps.org/geoserver/na-mespace/wms?service=WMS&version=1.1.0&request=GetMap&layers=LAYER1,LAYER5>).

These parameters allow users to specify which layer(s) of the WMS shall be used. The uploaded overlay will contain all the layers specified in the layers-parameter of the URL (i.e. LAYER1, LAYER5 from the example URL). A newly uploaded overlay will be highlighted and appears at the top of the list of already uploaded overlays (see Figure 6a).

Figure 5: (1.) The volume overview page with the edit-button to get to (2.) the volume edit page (red frame). The geo-overlays panel is highlighted in the bottom right corner. Here, the users can choose between two available upload mechanisms (by selecting one of the tabs in the geo-overlays panel, i.e. geoTIFF, or WMS). Below the upload mechanism, users are presented a table of uploaded overlays, together with the possibility to enable/disable the overlay for either of the new features as well as to delete it.

Once the geo-overlays are uploaded, there are two options to use them within the volume. The option is selected by enabling/disabling the "Browsing"- and "Context"-buttons within the list of uploaded overlays (individually for each uploaded overlay):

1. An enabled "Browsing"-button will display the overlay on the map-interface of the "geo-selection" filter.
2. An enabled "Context"-button makes the overlay available as a context-layer / background-layer in the annotation view of BIIGLE.

It is also possible to sort the overlays according to the order they should appear on the map (top to bottom = highest to lowest layer) by dragging an overlay from the list to the desired position by holding the hamburger-button (See Figure 6b).

Figure 6: a) A newly uploaded overlay will be highlighted and positioned at the top of the overlays list. b) It is possible to re-position the overlay by dragging it to the desired position.

This determines the order in which they will appear on the map (top to bottom = highest to lowest layer).

Technical implementation

The two new features were implemented following BIIGLE's general modular design, i.e. they were developed in their own BIIGLE module, which is installable as a Git repository (biigle/geo). BIIGLE itself is a web application written in the PHP and JavaScript languages with the Laravel and Vue.js application frameworks. A deployment of the software is based on a Nginx webserver, PHP-FPM application server and PostgreSQL database as Docker containers managed by Docker Compose.

The two features and the upload mechanism were developed on the basis of BIIGLE's technological backbone.

The upload of files is handled in the Laravel backend which is based on PHP. For the WMS upload, we had to parse information in xml-format which was fetched from the provided URL's. This is natively supported by PHP.

For the geoTIFF upload it was not as straight forward. One challenge in the development was, that a well maintained GDAL wrapper for PHP does not exist (which is the most commonly used library for reading / translating geospatial data formats). So without any GDAL utilities (or equivalent PHP-wrappers) available, we decided to write the functions to parse the geospatial data ourselves, as we wanted to avoid calling an external script due to performance reasons. Therefore, we needed an additional dependency (PHP-exif) in order to parse the exif-tags of the .tif files. Once the information was accessible, we consistently transformed the coordinate system from whatever original model-space into the WGS84 projection (or EPSG:4326), using the open source library Proj4php. This geographical information served as the basis for the visualisation in the application frontend. To see/interact with this information on maps and/or on background layers, the open source package OpenLayers (v.9.2.4) was used.

b) Data and Software availability

The software was implemented as its own BIIGLE module in a Git repository (biigle/geo) and will be made available in the public BIIGLE instance (<https://biigle.de/>). The relevant commits to this pilot are comprised in the two issues for the features (geospatial browsing visualisation and geospatial context fusion display). The BIIGLE software is open source and can be used under the MIT License. The new features and functionality as described in Chapter 2 a) will also be made explicit in the BIIGLE manual (<https://biigle.de/manual>). The new functions will be announced through the BIIGLE newsletter, in BIIGLE user meetings (next one in February 2025) and on social media (X/twitter). In addition, we are planning to write a new BIIGLE paper to be published in 2025 and the new functions will be described there as well.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

BIIGLE itself (and including the new functions) is a pioneering software tool to implement the image FAIR Digital Object concept (iFDOs, see also above in IIa.) for marine, terrestrial and planetary imagery. Other elements of the FAIR image infrastructure were provided through collaboration partners such as GEOMAR (e.g. handle server to enable persistent identification of georeferenced grids, image data sets and potentially label catalogs as well as an OAI-PMH catalog service to publish the availability of image data set and maps for data re-use). As such, this project brought several data management and infrastructure concepts and FAIR data principles (like iFDOs) into operationality for earth system scientists.

III. Challenges and Gaps

The roadmap for the pilot was discussed at the beginning of the project, with a timeline of tasks that need to be tackled and their estimated cost (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: The project timeline with tasks (colored steps) and estimated time, as anticipated at the beginning of the project.

Our expectations were that most time will be required for the context fusion feature, as it is more of an experimental feature, and it was less clear at the beginning how it can be (technically) realised as compared to the geospatial browsing and filtering mechanism. Despite some changes in the time schedule, we still managed to realise both features successfully within the given timeframe.

The development of the first feature (Filtering) went as expected and was even finished a bit earlier than anticipated. Implementing the “Upload” feature required more time as expected, due to the problem mentioned in IIa. above (i.e. no GDAL library for translating geospatial data available) and to avoid any performance issues we had to implement the relevant functions to parse the geospatial data ourselves. As a consequence, the geoTIFF, needs to be in a standard format before it can be uploaded. The following restrictions apply to the geoTIFF upload:

- requires a Projected Coordinate Reference System (CRS) (not working with Geodetic CRS)
- requires a reference to an EPSG CRS code (not working with a user-defined or undefined projection [ProjectedCSType]).

A second challenge in this step was the visualization itself. To prepare the geoTIFF for the web visualization in BIIGLE, the original file is automatically chopped into smaller tiles (of 256x256 pixels) which could then be loaded with a tiling function (only displaying those tiles that happen to be within the current viewport of the map). The transformation from the .tif to tiled .jpeg images comes at the cost of a potential information loss, as geoTIFF's can have higher original signal/colour resolution. To avoid unwanted result signal shifts in this step, we used the open source image processing library libvips with its existing PHP binding to normalize the values before the tiling process whenever they differed from the 0 to 255 range.

But, since geoTIFF's may also contain NoData-values (resulting in the black bounding box around the geoTIFF when transformed to .jpeg tiles), BIIGLE manual mentions the two following criteria for geoTIFF files in order to be rendered correctly:

- Make sure that the color-band of the geoTIFF is normalized to the range of 0 to 255.
- If the color-band differs (e.g. negative range), the normalization can also be handled by BIIGLE if the NoData values of the geoTIFF are set to -99999.

As building the upload mechanism required more resources than anticipated, there was less time left for the context fusion feature. However, we were still able to develop an operational prototype for this feature (see Figure 4). Since the context-layer should align with a single

image, the quality of the result crucially depends on the quality of the underlying data. First, we acquired a dataset from PANGEA that included a) a mosaic as well as the individual images and b) those sources having all the relevant information required for a decent alignment of a single image and the mosaic (i.e. geo-coordinates of the single image and the mosaic, yaw/rotation of the image, and pixel to unit ratio of each image and the mosaic). The problem to find such a dataset is rooted within the mosaic algorithms that create image mosaics, as they do not necessarily save all information on the scaling, stitching, and rotating of the images. And when such data exists, this information would also need to be included by the researchers or institutions publishing their data. As can be seen in Chapter IIa) Figure 4, the implemented context-fusion mechanism shows some decent results based on the provided data. But there were also quite a few instances in the dataset where the estimated metadata information did not match as well as in this example (see Figure 8). Despite the results being highly dependent on the data quality, a further limitation is the availability of all necessary metadata information. As mentioned in Chapter 2, information such as the pixel-to-unit ratio's of both sources are less likely to be contained in the metadata as compared to, e.g. the geo-coordinates of each source. Therefore, we added the option to manually adjust the scale of the context-layer to the prototype.

Figure 8: Two examples of mismatches between the context-layer/mosaic and the single image due to the underlying data quality (red frames were added for better identification of single images).

Moreover, being able to draw on the existing open source software libraries did not only accelerate the implementation, it also helped us in terms of closing knowledge gaps or accessing expertise through a strong community behind these tools. As an example: We were trying to get the reprojections of the tiled geoTIFF overlays right so that they were showing up as expected on the map. As we didn't find the right solution from the documentation of the OpenLayers library alone, we asked the community for help, and received a helping answer in no time.

In a similar fashion, the NFDI4Earth community helped in the sense of exchanging ideas regarding common issues within the domain. For instance, we were able to exchange some ideas on the NFDI4Earth-plenary with a fellow Pilot developer, Jonas Lenz from SoilPulse, regarding the PHP/GDAL issue and potential solutions.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

BIIGLE and the new functions developed in this pilot contribute to the data value chain, particularly through improving the efficiency and effectiveness in human image interpretation. Thereby it also supports harvesting human expert knowledge to collect more training data for the tuning of AI systems. The two new functions (like the entire BIIGLE system) address different steps of the research data life cycle, like *Data Analysis* (like manual/automatic annotation), *Preserving Data* (sustainable management of taxonomic catalogs) or *Giving Access to Data* (including map data/mosaics in the annotation process). By providing spatial context, data re-use capacity becomes easier to assess and as such BIIGLE will become operational to further support the data acquisition planning step of the data life cycle.

V. Future Directions

Future developments in the BIIGLE system may point in three directions. The first direction aims at improving features to the BIIGLE system like improving data import / export regarding AI applications and improving the two new functions implemented in this project. Improvements may include interactive tuning of the map / mosaic visualization for instance or improved interfaces to data servers. The second direction is adding more AI functionality to BIIGLE. Recently, new features like SAM (segment anything model) or a feature similarity sorting in the LARGO interface have been added but more AI functions, like an updated MAIA tool will be of great value to the users. The third direction could be the implementation of a hyperspectral image viewer with annotation function.